

POPULATION DYNAMICS OF PLANT PARASITIC NEMATODES AND THEIR RELATION TO SOIL PROPERTIES IN TEA

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Abstract

A study was conducted to assess the occurrence of plant parasitic nematodes (PPNs) and their relationship with soil properties from July to December 2015 at the Lackatoorah, Malnicherra, and Ali Bahar tea estates in the North Sylhet region of Bangladesh. Rhizosphere soil samples were taken at a depth of 23 cm from the primary nursery bed, secondary nursery bed, first-year plantation, and second-year plantation of the selected tea estates. Root samples were also collected from four locations of the above tea estates. Nematodes were extracted from the soil samples using the Baermann funnel method. Physico-chemical properties of the soil like textural class, sand (%), silt (%), clay (%), pH, and organic matter (%) from different locations of the aforementioned tea gardens were also determined to find out their relationship with nematodes population. The result revealed that out of 60 collected soil samples from different locations of selected tea estates, 47 were infested with PPNS with frequencies of 78.33%. The average frequency of occurrence was maximum (90.00%) and minimum (65.00%) in the soil samples of the Malnicherra and Lackatoorah tea estates, respectively. The highest frequency of PPNS was observed in the soil samples of the secondary nursery bed of selected tea gardens, with a frequency of 93.00%. The maximum frequency of occurrence (80.00%) was observed in the root samples of the secondary nursery bed, and that was the minimum (26.67%) in the second-year plantation. The highest numbers of PPNS were observed in the soil of the Malnicherra tea estate, followed by Lackatoorah and Ali Bahar tea estates. The mean numbers of PPNS were lowest in soil and root samples of second-year plantations from all the tea estates. According to pH, the selected tea estates were under moderately acidic soil with a range of 4.3-5.0. Three types of soil texture were found in different tea estates: sandy, sandy loam, and sandy clay loam. The highest nematode population was observed in sandy loam soil, and the lowest was in sandy soil. Maximum PPN was found in the sand, silt, and clay within the range of 70-80%, 8-13%, and 9-18%, respectively. The population of PPNS was linearly and positively correlated with soil pH and organic matter (%) in all three tea estates.

Keywords: Tea, Plant parasitic nematodes, Rhizosphere soil, Soil properties

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Introduction

Nematodes are a type of soil pest also known as eelworms. They may be parasitic, feeding on the roots of plants as ectoparasites or endoparasites, or saprophagous, feeding on decomposing organic materials (Mamun, 2019; Paul et al., 2017; Roy & Rahman, 2013). It can be found worldwide in a wide range of habitats. The PPNS are an important pest of many cultivated plants, including rice, fruits, vegetables, legumes, tea, coffee, cocoa, etc. Nematode infestation is a slow change; plants don't show symptoms until a substantial portion of the root system has been lost or stopped functioning. The first indicators of nematode attack are a slowdown in growth, then yellowing and wilting of leaves. In severe conditions, die-back and death could occur (Mamun et al., 2014; Paul et al., 2014). In various tea-growing nations around the world, there are over 40 species of PPNS from 20 genera (Gnanapragasam, 2014; Mamun et al., 2011; Mohotti et al., 2023). Twelve species of PPNS, namely *Xiphinema* sp., *Tylenchus* sp., *Rotylenchulus* sp., *Pratylenchus* sp., *Meloidogyne* sp., *Hoplolaimus* sp., *Helicotylenchus* sp., *Eutylenchus* sp., *Dolichodorus* sp., *Criconemoides* sp., *Aphelenchoides* sp., and *Aphelenchus* sp., in tea soil, are recorded from Bangladesh (Paul et al., 2019). The PPNS cause crop losses of more than 100 billion US\$ each year all over the world (Dias-Arieira et al., 2021). The PPNS cause a loss of 5-10%, or even up to 50%, in producing healthy tea seedlings, depending on the severity of the infestation (Roy & Rahman, 2013). One of the important ways that infestation spreads among tea estates is through infected nursery plants. Understandably, nematodes cannot be eliminated after they have been introduced to an area. Additionally, harm to young seedlings at their crucial growth stage has a long-term effect on the plant's health throughout its lifetime (Gnanapragasam, 2014).

Tea can be cultivated on soils with varying geological origins. The majority of the soils in Bangladesh are alluvial sedimentary soils. Bangladesh tea soil is highly acidic and extensively degraded, with lower fertility. Most soils have a medium texture and low nitrogen (1.0-1.2 percent) and organic matter (0.70-0.90 percent) contents. Most of Bangladesh's tea soils are loamy in texture. Additionally, the exchangeable sites in Bangladesh tea soil have more than 85% aluminium (Alam, 1999; Sana, 1989). Numerous abiotic and biotic factors may impact the spatial pattern of nematodes in the soil (Kemboi et al., 2022; Olabiyi et al., 2009). Most plant-parasitic nematodes tend to have their maximum population numbers in the top 45 cm of the soil profile (Fajardo et al., 2011), with their vertical distribution somewhat influenced by the host's rooting pattern (Bhattacharya et al., 2012). According to Ferris et al. (1996), the host plant, with its food source, is the most significant factor influencing nematode dispersion in the soil. Moreover, abiotic factors, viz. temperature, soil physico-chemical properties, and moisture, may substantially impact nematodes' quantity, distribution, and structure in the host's roots and soil (Krif et al., 2020; Upadhaya et al., 2019).

The information on the status of population dynamics of PPNs and their relationship with soil physico-chemical properties in the North Sylhet region is scanty. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to know the population dynamics of PPNs in tea soil of the North Sylhet region and to determine the relationship between nematode populations and soil properties in tea.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted in the Ali Bahar, Lackatoorah, and Malnicherra tea estates of the North Sylhet region from July to December 2015. Soil samples were collected from four different locations of nursery and young tea plantations from each tea estate, such as primary and secondary nursery beds as well as first and second-year plantations.

Collection of soil samples

Using a sampling auger, soil samples were taken from the root zone of the tea plants up to a depth of 23 cm and up to 5 cm from the base of the plants. Five beds from primary and secondary nursery areas and five spots from first and second-year plantations from each tea estate were randomly selected for soil sample collection. Every sample comprised a composite of 5 soil cores from each location of the selected tea estates. Twenty composite samples were prepared from each tea estate. In the case of root samples, 5 plants were selected arbitrarily from each location of the selected tea estates. Twenty root samples were also collected from each tea estate. Thus a total of 120 soil and root samples were collected from different locations of the above tea estates. The samples were placed in plastic bags, sealed to avoid desiccation, and kept out of sunlight. They were transported in a shielded bag and stored at 4°C to minimize changes in nematode populations. Every time the samples were mixed thoroughly, 10 g of soil and 10 g of root sample were made for nematode extraction. For analysis of soil properties, one composite sample was prepared by mixing 5 subsamples for each location with the rest of the soils after nematode extraction. Thus, 12 soil samples were made, and a 250 g sample was analyzed for soil properties.

Nematode extraction from soil

Nematode extraction and identification from soil and root were carried out in the Nematology Laboratory of the Entomology Division, BTRI, Sreemangal, Moulvibazar. Nematodes were extracted from the samples following the Baermann funnel technique with some modifications (Mian, 1998). Nematodes were taken in a glass slide with a drop of water by loosening the pinch clamp. Nematodes were examined using a Primostar Trinocular compound microscope (Carl Zeiss) with 100X objectives to distinguish between plant-parasitic (PPNs) and non-parasitic (NPNs) nematodes. Plant parasitic nematodes bear stylet at the anterior end of their mouth part, which can be protruded and used to penetrate plant cells like a hypodermic needle. A mean of three counts was taken in each case.

Analysis of soil properties

Soil properties viz. pH, sand%, silt%, clay%, texture, and organic matter were analyzed in the Soil Science Division of BTRI to know their relationship with the nematode population. A pH meter was used to calculate soil pH (soil: distilled water = 1: 2.5). Sand, silt, and clay fractions were determined by the hydrometer method. Textural classes were selected from the Marshall (1947) triangular diagram. The Walkley and Black wet oxidation method was used to calculate the soil organic carbon (Huq & Alam, 2005), and organic matter was calculated by multiplying the organic carbon by 1.72.

Data analysis

The average number of nematodes in 3 different drops of water was used to calculate the number of nematodes. The frequency of PPN was determined from the relationship between the number of samples in which PPNs were observed divided by the total number of samples taken from that tea estate multiplied by 100 to express as a percentage (Norton et al., 1978). Regression analysis determined the relationship between nematode population and soil properties. All collected data were subjected to analysis using the MS Excel program.

Results and Discussion*Nematodes associated with soil and root samples*

Among 60 soil samples, 13 samples have found the nonexistence of PPNs. Regarding root samples, 22 samples have been found free of PPNs. The frequencies of the nematodes in all surveyed tea gardens varied from one garden to another. The overall frequency of PPN occurrence was 78.33% and 63.33% in soil and root, respectively. The frequency of occurrence was maximum (90.00%) in the soil samples of the Malnicherra tea estate and minimum (65.00%) in the Lackatoorah tea estate. On the other hand, the frequency of occurrence was maximum (75.00%) in the root samples of the Malnicherra tea estate and minimum (50.00%) in the Lackatoorah tea estate (Table 1).

Table 1. Frequency of occurrence of PPNs in soils and root samples of three tea estates in the North Sylhet region.

Name of tea estate	Sample analyzed		Sample with PPN		Frequency of PPN (%)±SE	
	Soil	Root	Soil	Root	Soil	Root
Ali Bahar Tea Estate	20	20	16	13	80.00±2.13	65.00±1.95
Lackatoorah Tea Estate	20	20	13	10	65.00±1.52	50.00±1.13
Malnicherra Tea Estate	20	20	18	15	90.00±2.51	75.00±2.21

PPN= Plant Parasitic Nematode; SE= Standard Error

Table 2 shows the frequency of occurrence of PPNs in different locations of selected tea estates in the North Sylhet region. Results revealed that the soil samples from secondary beds of chosen tea gardens were infested with PPNs with a frequency of 93.00%, followed by the soil samples from first-year plantations (86.66%). The lowest frequency of PPNs (60.00) was found in the soil samples of the second-year plantation. In the root samples, the maximum frequency of occurrence (80.00%) was observed in the secondary nursery bed, which was the lowest (26.67%) in the second-year plantation.

Table 2. Frequency of occurrence of PPNs in soils and root samples in different locations of three tea estates in the North Sylhet region.

Location	Sample analyzed		Sample with PPN		Frequency of PPN (%)±SE	
	Soil	Root	Soil	Root	Soil	Root
Primary nursery bed	15	15	12	10	80.00±1.11	66.67±1.25
Secondary nursery bed	15	15	14	12	93.00±2.01	80.00±2.12
First-year plantation	15	15	13	09	86.66±1.53	60.00±1.44
Second-year plantation	15	15	09	04	60.00±1.65	26.67±1.02

PPN= Plant Parasitic Nematode; SE= Standard Error

Table 3 shows the mean number of nematodes found in soil and root samples, including the frequency of occurrence of PPNs in different locations of selected tea estates. In the case of the Ali Bahar tea estate, the highest frequency of PPNs was found in the soil of the secondary bed (21.83%),

followed by the first-year plantation (18.21%), and the lowest was found in the second-year plantation (10.54%) (Table 3a). In the Lackatoorah tea estate, the highest frequency of PPNs was found in first-year plantations (22.09%), and those were 20.47% and 15.78% in secondary beds and primary beds, respectively (Table 3b). It was also observed that the soil samples from the secondary bed of the Malnicherra tea estate contained the highest frequency of PPNs (27.49%), followed by first-year plantation (26.36%) and primary bed (19.92%) (Table 3c). Results also showed that the frequency of occurrence of PPNs in the entire root samples of selected tea gardens was 100%.

Table 3. Mean number and percentage of PPN in different locations.

Location	PPN (no.)±SE		NPN (no.)±SE		Total (no.)±SE		Frequency of PPN (%)±SE	
	Soil	Root	Soil	Root	Soil	Root	Soil	Root
a. Ali Bahar Tea Estate								
Primary nursery bed	10.11±1.12	6.20±0.14	50.11±2.33	0.00	60.22±3.01	6.20±0.14	16.79±2.01	100.00
Secondary nursery bed	11.21±1.35	8.14±0.36	40.15±1.52	0.00	51.36±1.84	8.14±0.36	21.83±2.53	100.00
First-year plantation	13.41±1.03	4.03±0.27	60.23±2.74	0.00	73.64±2.14	4.03±0.27	18.21±1.43	100.00
Second-year plantation	5.32±1.54	2.01±0.22	45.16±1.47	0.00	50.48±1.71	2.01±0.22	10.54±1.12	100.00
b. Lackatoorah Tea Estate								
Primary nursery bed	12.22±1.02	7.13±0.27	65.24±2.17	0.00	77.46±2.89	7.13±0.27	15.78±1.13	100.00
Secondary nursery bed	15.01±1.55	11.18±0.34	58.33±1.52	0.00	73.34±2.24	11.18±0.34	20.47±1.47	100.00
First-year plantation	13.46±1.32	9.27±0.14	47.47±1.14	0.00	60.93±1.42	9.27±0.14	22.09±2.01	100.00
Second-year plantation	6.15±1.17	3.16±0.11	70.00±2.46	0.00	76.15±1.76	3.16±0.11	8.08±1.05	100.00
c. Malnicherra Tea Estate								
Primary nursery bed	15.23±0.74	12.13±0.11	61.23±1.14	0.00	76.46±2.33	12.13±0.11	19.92±1.22	100.00
Secondary nursery bed	14.03±0.51	9.22±0.24	37.00±1.21	0.00	51.03±1.72	9.22±0.24	27.49±1.59	100.00
First-year plantation	17.34±0.83	10.11±0.31	48.45±1.43	0.00	65.79±1.86	10.11±0.31	26.36±1.33	100.00
Second-year plantation	8.12±0.39	3.07±0.14	73.31±1.33	0.00	81.43±2.55	3.07±0.14	9.97±1.04	100.00

PPN= Plant Parasitic Nematode; NPN= Non-Parasitic Nematode; SE= Standard Error

Figure 1a shows the mean population number of PPNs in different locations of three tea estates. The mean numbers of PPNs were highest in the secondary nursery bed and the lowest was in the second-year plantation. Figure 1b demonstrates the average number of PPNs in three tea estates of the North Sylhet region. The Malnicherra tea estate had the most PPNs, followed by Lackatoorah and Ali Bahar tea estates.

Fig. 1. The mean number of PPN in different locations (a) of selected tea estates (b). Vertical lines at each bar indicate the SE value

It was observed that the nematode population varied with different locations, tea estates, and ages of tea plants in all the surveyed tea estates. The survey provided information on the frequency and average population of PPNs associated with tea soil in the North Sylhet region. In general, 78.33% of the samples had a PPNs population, which was high enough to initiate a potential for damage and contribute the most significant portion of the risk. The tea plant is a good host of PPNs, and different species of nematodes infect the tea plant (Ahmed, 2005; Bhattacharya et al., 2012; Khan et al., 2006; Nalini et al., 2005; Paul et al., 2019; Roy & Rahman, 2013). This study found that the root samples of second-year plantations from all the tea estates had the lowest number of PPNs. This may be because the PPNs cannot easily suck the roots of second-year tea plants due to their hard epidermis. This corroborates earlier works that reported soil depth and crop growth stage affect the population density of nematodes in corn fields (Simon et al., 2023).

Relationship between nematode population and soil properties

Data presented in Table 4 elucidate the textural class, the percentage of sand, silt, clay, organic matter (%), and pH of the Lackatoorah, Malnicherra, and Ali Bahar tea estates in the North Sylhet region. The tested soils from the Lackatoorah tea estate, with a pH range of 4.4-5.0, were moderately acidic (Table 4a). Similarly, the pH range of the Malnicherra tea estate was 4.5-5.1 (Table 4b), and that of the Ali Bahar tea estate was 4.5-5.0 (Table 4c), which is also moderately acidic.

The soil textural class in different locations of the Lackatoorah tea estate was found in sandy loam, sandy clay loam, and sandy (Table 4a). On the other hand, sandy loam and sandy clay loam textured soil were found in Malnicherra and Ali Bahar tea estates (Table 4b, c). Results revealed that soil textural class affected the average number of nematode populations in different locations of selected tea estates. The highest PPNs were observed in sandy loam soil next to sandy clay loam, and the lowest PPNs were observed in sandy soil (Figure 2a).

Different textural types were found due to the varying amounts of sand, silt, and clay. In sandy loam soil, the percent of sand, silt, and clay ranged from 70.00-81.00%, 8.00-12.80%, and 7.00-17.75%, respectively (Table 4). Whereas the percent of sand, silt, and clay were 90.00%, 0.00%, and 10.00%, respectively, in sandy soil, and those were within the range of 53.40-54.30%, 16.30-17.40%, and 28.30-30.30% respectively (Table 4). Maximum PPNs were found in the percent of sand, silt, and clay within the range of 70-80%, 8-13%, and 9-18%, respectively (Figure 2b, c, d). On the other hand, the populations of PPNs were positively correlated with soil pH with co-efficient of determination (R^2) values were 0.79, 0.84, and 0.79 for Lackatoorah, Malnicherra, and Ali Bahar tea estates, respectively (Figure 3a, c, e). Organic matter (%) was also positively correlated with PPN populations, with R^2 values were 0.84, 0.79, and 0.81 for Lackatoorah, Malnicherra, and Ali Bahar tea estates, respectively (Figure 3b, d, f).

Table 4. Soil physico-chemical properties of selected tea estates in the North Sylhet region.

a. Lackatoorah Tea Estate						
Location of soil sample	Textural class	Sand(%)±SE	Silt(%)±SE	Clay(%)±SE	pH±SE	OM(%)±SE
Primary nursery bed	Sandy clay loam	55.16±0.51	17.65±0.23	27.19±0.21	4.6±0.11	1.46±0.01
Secondary nursery bed	Sandy loam	80.00±0.73	10.00±0.32	10.00±0.11	5.0±0.08	1.72±0.08
First-year plantation	Sandy loam	70.40±0.42	11.85±0.53	17.75±0.33	4.7±0.04	1.55±0.02
Second-year plantation	Sandy	90.00±0.65	1.03±0.17	8.17±0.28	4.4±0.05	1.34±0.09
b. Malnicherra Tea Estate						
Primary nursery bed	Sandy loam	81.00±0.65	12.00±0.31	7.00±0.23	4.8±0.07	1.48±0.11
Secondary nursery bed	Sandy loam	78.20±0.48	12.80±0.22	9.00±0.17	5.1±0.09	1.69±0.05
First-year plantation	Sandy clay loam	53.40±0.34	16.30±0.14	30.30±0.21	4.5±0.06	1.20±0.08
Second-year plantation	Sandy clay loam	54.30±0.25	17.40±0.42	28.30±0.33	4.7±0.04	1.38±0.06
c. Ali Bahar Tea Estate						
Primary nursery bed	Sandy clay loam	55.00±0.41	16.10±0.23	28.90±0.14	4.5±0.10	1.29±0.03
Secondary nursery bed	Sandy loam	70.00±0.33	9.40±0.11	15.20±0.08	5.0±0.08	1.72±0.05
First-year plantation	Sandy loam	76.80±1.01	8.00±0.09	17.20±0.25	4.7±0.04	1.53±0.07
Second-year plantation	Sandy loam	76.23±0.74	10.47±0.12	13.30±0.09	4.8±0.06	1.48±0.04

SE= Standard Error

Soil pH, texture, organic matter content, moisture, rainfall, temperature, and plant type influence the population density of nematodes in tea (Bhattacharya et al., 2012; Khan et al., 2006). Diverse soil pH, texture, and organic matter (%) were found in different locations of the tea estates during this study. Asif et al. (2015) and Choshali et al. (2015) reported that some species of PPNs were higher in sandy loam or lighter soils, which enhanced nematode movement. This report supports the findings of this study. Another study by Paiko et al. (2019) reported that PPNs were negatively correlated with sandy soil, similar to the present study's findings. The report further showed that soil pH was positively correlated with certain species of PPNs. Khan et al. (2006) and Bhattacharya et al. (2012) found a positive correlation between the PPNs population and the organic matter content of tea soil.

Fig. 2. Influence of (a) soil texture, (b) sand%, (c) silt%, and (d) clay% on nematode population in selected tea estates in North Sylhet region. Vertical lines at each bar indicate the SE value.

Fig. 3. Relationship of pH and organic matter (%) on nematode population in Lackatoorah (a, b), Malnicherra (c, d), and Ali Bahar (e, f) tea estates.

Conclusion

This study provides the population dynamics of PPNs and shows their relationship to soil properties in tea plantations. Overall, 78.33% of soil samples were infected with PPNs. The average frequency of occurrence was maximum (90.00%) and minimum (65.00%) in the soil samples of the Malnicherra and Lackatoorah tea estates, respectively. The highest frequencies of occurrence were observed in soil (93.00%) and root (80.00%) samples of secondary nursery beds of selected tea gardens. The highest nematode numbers were found in sandy loam soil. Maximum PPN was found in the percent of sand, silt, and clay within the range of 70-80%, 8-13%, and 9-18%, respectively. A linear and positive correlation existed between the PPN population and organic matter (%) and soil pH in all three tea plantations. The study on PPNs in tea would be helpful to know the density of nematodes in soil and their degree of damage. The influence of soil properties on the nematode population would be beneficial to ensure a better selection of soil medium and optimization of soil properties in tea plantations. Further research on the relationship of physico-chemical parameters with major plant PPNs in Bangladesh tea can be done extensively in other tea plantations of different locations.

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